

Effects of perceived organisational support on participation in decision making, affective commitment and job satisfaction in lean production in Sri Lanka

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Purpose- To examine the moderating effect of perceived organisational support (POS) on the relationship between participation in decision making (PDM) and affective commitment, and PDM and job satisfaction in lean production in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- A random sample of 616 shop-floor employees engaged full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms, which have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and where lean production has become the standard of operation for at least one year in Sri Lanka, responded. Regression analysis was used to test hypotheses.

Findings- Perceived organisational support moderates the relationship between PDM and affective commitment, and PDM and job satisfaction.

Originality/value- The literature suggests that the bottom-line changes often cited in lean implementation success stories, such as reduced inventories and faster flow times, are not the only results that should be considered. The potential detrimental effects on employees should be considered as well, or turnover and morale problems may sabotage the effectiveness of such implementations. However, the manner in which the lean production environment influences employee behaviour has received scant empirical attention. The findings of this study provide interesting implications to practice and will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Key words: Affective commitment, Job satisfaction, Lean production, Participation in decision making, Perceived organisational support.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Lean production is an advanced production practice that has evolved beyond its origins (Womack et al., 1990) in the auto industry. It creates a streamlined production system by synergistically implementing a bundle of management practices, such as total quality management, just-in-time (JIT), *kaizen* or continuous improvement, quality circles, and total

productive maintenance (Bonavia and Marin, 2006; Browning and Heath, 2009; González-Benito, 2005; Shah and Ward, 2003; Zhang et al., 2006). Some authors identify human resource management as another associated practice that facilitates or limits the adoption of lean production (e.g. Forza, 1996; MacDuffie, 1995a; Santos, 2000; Shah and Ward, 2003).

Work systems conducive to lean production involves several core characteristics, such as a multi-skilled workforce taking a high degree of responsibility for work within their areas, the interaction of groups of individuals from parallel structures in the formal organisation with a requisite variety in knowledge and capabilities, and active shop-floor problem-solving structures that are central to *kaizen* (Forza, 1996; Fullerton and Wempe, 2009; González-Benito, 2005). These characteristics demand employee participation in decision making (PDM) to be an integral aspect of a successful lean production process (Co et al, 1998; Conti et al., 2006; Fullerton and Wempe, 2009). Yet, scholars criticise the work systems of lean production for being exploitative and high pressure to the shop-floor employees (e.g. Hines et al., 2004). However, there is surprisingly little empirical research addressing the influence of participatory work arrangements on employee work attitudes in the operations management literature (e.g. Brown and Mitchell, 1991; Conti et al., 2006; Forza, 1996; Harrison and Storey, 1996; McLachlin, 1997). In a study that investigated the human resource issues in the just-in-time (JIT) implementation, Brown and Mitchell (1991) found that human related performance obstacles in the work environment that prevent people from performing their jobs to the best of their abilities had increased in importance after the implementation of JIT. As employees in the JIT system are highly dependent on their group members, they perceived greater obstacles than the batch employees in the area of reliance on co-workers (Brown and Mitchell, 1991). Hence, Brown and Mitchell (1991) conclude that the bottom-line changes often cited in the JIT success stories, such as reduced inventories and faster flow times, are not the only results that should be considered. The potential for detrimental effects on employees should be considered as well, or turnover and morale problems may sabotage the effectiveness of JIT implementation.

Therefore, on the one hand, such findings have to be assessed over a variety of samples using similar and different research methodologies. However, our review of literature has shown that employee beliefs and attitudes to various dimensions of advanced manufacturing systems have not yet received due attention. A few case studies (e.g. Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Harrison and Storey, 1996; Niepce and Molleman, 1996; Scherrer-Rathje et al., 2009), quantitative questionnaire surveys (e.g. Forza, 1996; Co et al., 1998; Conti et al., 2006) and a qualitative interview survey (e.g. Vidal, 2007) have so far attempted to address various aspects of human dimension in lean production. Therefore, there is no consensus regarding the extent to which, and ways in which, the adoption of lean production has implications for human resources, especially, human resources on the shop-floor (see Hines et al., 2004). On the other hand, the work organisation of lean production should be able to balance the needs of the organisation as well as the psychosocial needs of employees for efficiency (see Niepce and Molleman, 1996). In this regard, Hines et al. (2004) suggest that academics and practitioners interested in applying lean thinking should consider various aspects of human dimension as very important. However, the treatment of work organisation in advanced manufacturing systems in the organisational behaviour literature remains partial because of its failure to engage fully with operational arrangements (see Conti et al., 2006; Harrison and Storey, 1996). Therefore, there is a need to investigate various aspects of human dimension in the operations management literature to understand how employee participation contributes to gains for both employees and employers.

Further, the literature on operations management themes describes application contexts in North America, Western Europe as well as countries in the Asia-Pacific region such as Australia and Japan. However, valuable lessons could be learned from implementation experiences in different parts of the world, especially in South Asia. In response to several factors, such as increasing global competition, low labour costs in Sri Lanka and inducements from the Sri Lankan government, the number of international businesses coming into the country has been increasing. In the context of globalisation of business operations and interlocking supply chains, a research on lean production systems in South Asia (Sri Lanka in

particular) is interesting, relevant and timely since there is a dearth of empirical research that explains human dimension in the operations management context in this part of the world.

In the above context, by taking into account how PDM affects job satisfaction and affective commitment and how perceived organisational support (POS) influences the relationship, the study tested the role of POS as a moderator between PDM and job satisfaction and affective commitment of shop-floor employees in export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka (refer to Figure 1). With regard to the treatment of POS in the previous research studies, some treated it as an independent variable (e.g. Chen et al., 2009) while some others treated it as a mediator variable (e.g. Cheung and Law, 2008) depending on the context of the study. The current study treats POS, in the context of lean production, as a moderator where POS operates to strengthen the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction, and PDM and affective commitment. For the study, quantitative research methodology was used and data was collected from 616 shop-floor employees engaged full-time in all the 12 export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka. On the one hand, it is expected that the findings presented in this article will be able to provide practitioners with valid information for better managerial decision making in the context of lean production. On the other hand, the findings of this study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

In order to provide the context for the article, the next section briefly describes the Sri Lankan context and reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Background of the study: Sri Lankan context

The export-apparel manufacturing industry is the leading manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka that has emerged as the country's main export earner and the largest single employment

provider in the industrial sector (Department of Census and Statistics, n.d). When producing apparel for the developed countries in the West, local manufactures have to strictly adhere to product design specifications provided by the foreign buyer, such as Marks and Spencer, who defines product design and quality.

The growth witnessed by this industry can be attributed to two major factors. First, the market-oriented liberal economic policies introduced in 1977 (Fonseka and Fonseka 1998). Second, the Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA), the worldwide system of managed trade in textiles and apparel that came into existence in 1974 (which subsequently integrated into the World Trade Organisation framework by 2005). The MFA introduced a quota system for the export of apparel products to developed countries by limiting the quantity of garments that can be exported by the developing countries to any single developed country. Therefore, the quota holding apparel exporting developing countries had been ensured a guaranteed market.

Due to rising wages and quota restrictions by MFA on East Asian economies (such as Hong Kong, South Korea and Taiwan, who were the leaders in apparel export by the late 1970s), export-apparel production shifted to quota holding Asian countries, such as Sri Lanka, Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia, China, India, and Pakistan in the late 1970s. Thereafter, export-apparel production has, further shifted to quota holding other countries with relatively lower labour cost in Asia (such as Laos, Cambodia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam), Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa (Fonseka and Fonseka 1998, p 255). Overall, under the quota regime, Sri Lanka like other apparel exporting developing countries had enjoyed a relatively assured export market through bilateral agreements with the developed world.

However, changes occurred when this system of managed trade perpetrated by MFA came to an end. The World Trade Organisation, which replaced GATT ushers a restriction-free world trade, set out a time period of 10 years from 1995 to 2005 to phase-out the MFA quota system and the integration of textiles and apparel export trade into the WTO framework. Export-apparel manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka faced this imminent phase-out of MFA quota system for the EU by the late 1990s and for the USA (and other Western countries) in 2005. In

real terms phasing out of the quota system challenged the very foundation on which this industry was built. Since the phase-out of the quota system by 2005, apparel exporting countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa have been competing intensively with each other for the market share. Since then, other competitive dimensions such as productivity and quality, therefore, have taken centre stage. This change of priorities has influenced rethinking operations management strategies adopted in this sector.

Since the mid 2000s, export-apparel manufacturers in Sri Lanka identified possibilities for them to turn to lean production for improving the efficiency of production systems. Scholars also suggest that rapid change industries adopt lean production as a growth paradigm (e.g. Duguay et al., 1997; Pirraglia et al., 2009). The attributes of lean production (see Womack et al., 1990, James-Moore and Gibbons, 1997; Hines et al., 2004), such as integrated, single piece production flow, low inventory, and close integration from raw material to customer through partnership fit with high-volume repetitive export-apparel manufacturing environment practicing in Sri Lanka. Preliminary investigations made by us revealed that export-apparel manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka are changing their production methods and management practices to become leaner and fitter to suit the new production model.

When considering the shop-floor workforce of this industry, workforce statistics (Department of Census and Statistics, n.d.) and past studies (Wickramasinghe, 2008) report that a majority of shop-floor employees are female, single, less than 25 years of age, and have secondary education less than or equal to 10 years of full-time education. Further, employees belonging to any category of the workforce of this industry are not unionised. However, it should be noted that the State interventions to protect the interests of the workers who do not have equal bargaining power with the employers has resulted in the enactment of a large number of labour statutes, where some argue that the Sri Lankan labour legislation is over protective of employees and weighs heavily in favour of them (Sarveswaran, n.d.). The platform indeed for the industry is better educated and trained employees; employers expect them to stay longer in a job. However, the industry suffers from a monthly average turnover rate of 8% for shop-floor

employees. Therefore, when capturing and capitalising on individual capabilities, there is a need to better understand work related attitudes of employees. Further, being in the export-apparel manufacturing industry for more than 30 years, the findings of this study will provide valuable information to both academics and practitioners as it is rare to find empirical evidence on human dimension in lean production.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Participation in decision making

Participation in decision-making refers to the sharing of decision making, which is ordinarily the prerogative or responsibility of a manager, with subordinates to achieve organizational objectives (Scott-Ladd et al., 2006; Stashevsky and Elizur, 2000). Employee PDM is central to lean production and it is higher in lean production plants than in traditional plants (Forza, 1996). For instance, eliminating scrap and rework is a determinant of the elimination of waste, which is the responsibility of employees. The identification of defective parts is also the responsibility of employees. Employees are allowed to stop the line in the event of finding defective parts and the responsibility for adjusting these defective parts is also delegated to employees. The commitment of each employee to continuous improvement is another key principle of lean production, which is often accomplished by implementing schemes for suggestions, quality circles, and spontaneous problem solving. The use of multifunctional teams, with multi-skilled employees, decreases the number of job classifications but increases the number of tasks in the team. The integration of different functions into teams means that tasks previously performed by indirect departments are integrated into the team, increasing the work content of the teams (see de Treville and Antonakis, 2006; Harrison and Storey, 1996; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Scherrer-Rathje et al., 2009). Therefore, on the one hand, employee participation increases flexibility and reduces the vulnerability of the production system (Forza, 1996).

On the other hand, organisational behaviour literature propagates that employee participation in solving production problems and devising process improvements increase job

control, which in turn associates with improvements in the quality of the work life of employees (e.g. Mulder, 1971). However, our review of literature suggests that little empirical research has directly addressed how employees in participatory work arrangements of the lean production respond to their work and the organisation (e.g. Vidal, 2007). Given the interest in society concerning the quality of the work life of employees in manufacturing settings (e.g., Conti et al., 2006; Vidal, 2007), PDM would appear to be a candidate for increased theoretical and empirical attention in the operations management literature. The organisational behaviour literature provides evidence that PDM is likely to reciprocate with positive job related attitudes towards the organisation (Scott-Ladd et al., 2006). Two of such job related attitudes are affective commitment and job satisfaction (Scott-Ladd et al., 2006).

In developing an account of the relationship between PDM and affective commitment and job satisfaction, in the following paragraphs, our focus is on specific literature that is relevant and useful for the current study. Further, for this study four hypotheses were developed as per the guidelines proposed by Fraizer et al. (2004) to test the moderation using hierarchical regression analysis (refer to the section on *data analysis procedure*).

Influence of PDM on affective commitment

Affective commitment refers to employees' sense of belonging and emotional attachment to the organisation, identification with the organisation's problems, and feeling that the organisation has personal meaning to oneself (Meyer et al., 1993). Affective commitment is, therefore, a linking of the identity of the individual with the identity of the organisation, which is described as an attachment to the organisation for its own sake, apart from its purely instrumental worth. Previous researchers found that an affectively committed employee is willing to exert effort towards achieving the most positive organisational outcomes in terms of performance (e.g. Meyer and Smith, 2000) and that he or she wants to continue his or her association with the organisation (Meyer et al., 1993).

The previous research within the organisational behaviour literature provides evidence that PDM increases employees' affective commitment (e.g. Scott-Ladd et al., 2006). In a study

conducted to explore work related outcomes of PDM in the lean production setting, Wickramasinghe (2008) surveyed 284 shop-floor employees from 6 out of 12 export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka and provides evidence for the existence of significant positive correlation between PDM and affective commitment. However, our review of journals has not been able to find any other studies that addressed the influence of participatory work arrangements on affective commitment in the lean production environment based on either quantitative or qualitative research methodology. Consistent with the past research, it is hypothesised for this study:

Hypothesis 1: PDM will be positively related to affective commitment.

Influence of PDM on job satisfaction

In this study, job satisfaction is conceptualised as a general attitude toward an object, the job (Cranny et al., 1992; Locke, 1976). Job satisfaction reveals an affective reaction to a job that results from an appraisal of a combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental job experiences, and a person's comparison of actual outcomes with those that are desired, anticipated or deserved (Locke, 1976).

PDM has been identified as a method of increasing employees' job satisfaction (e.g. Black and Gregersen, 1997; Miller and Monge, 1986). This is based on the premise that employees who can influence decisions are more likely to value the outcomes, which in turn reinforce their job satisfaction (Black and Gregersen, 1997). It is suggested that a higher level of job satisfaction comes with a higher level of PDM, as occurs when employees are involved in using important information, generating alternatives, planning processes, and evaluating results (Scott-Ladd et al., 2006). In other words, PDM satisfies higher-order psychological needs leading to a greater job satisfaction (Miller and Monge, 1986). Yammarino and Naughton (1992) found that individual as well as group level PDM creates shared perceptions that positively influence job satisfaction.

Although the organisational behaviour literature provides evidence that PDM increases job satisfaction (e.g. Scott-Ladd et al., 2006; Witt et al., 2000) our review of journals has been

able to find few studies that specifically addressed the influence of participatory work arrangements on job satisfaction in the lean production environment (e.g. MacDuffie, 1995b; Vidal, 2007; Wickramasinghe, 2008). In a study that addressed the influence of participatory work arrangements on job satisfaction in the lean production environment based on qualitative research methodology, Vidal (2007) found that a higher level of employee participation in the lean production process does not necessarily increase job satisfaction. Vidal (2007) further suggests that when participatory work arrangements involve substantial new responsibilities employees may experience those as burdens rather than challenges and consequently, swamp any direct effect of participation on job satisfaction. In contrast, MacDuffie (1995b) found that employees in lean production have new cognitive and social roles and they may respond favourably to these expanded roles. MacDuffie (1995b) further suggests that employees with prior experience in traditional mass production plants typically say they never want to go back to that setting. Further, Wickramasinghe (2008) provides evidence for the existence of significant positive correlation between PDM and job satisfaction in lean production in Sri Lanka. Therefore, consistent with the majority of the findings of the past research, it is hypothesised for this study:

Hypothesis 2: PDM will be positively related to job satisfaction.

Perceived organisational support

Perceived organisational support captures an employee's beliefs concerning the extent to which the organisation values [employees'] general contributions made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986, p. 501; Eisenberger et al., 2002, p. 566). In other words, POS focuses on the employer's side of the exchange as perceived by employees. Therefore, an employee's beliefs of how an organisation values him or her is vital for determining whether any attitudes or behaviours benefiting the organisation emerge from the exchange relationship that takes place between the employee and employer (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Shanock and Eisenberger, 2006).

It has been argued that POS is affected by the fair allocation of job rewards for the effort employees put in to meet organisational goals, which signify a belief that the organisation values the contribution of its employees (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002). Job rewards include tangible incentives, such as pay and fringe benefits and socio-emotional benefits such as esteem, supportive and helpful supervision, approval, and caring (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Further, employees value job rewards to be based on the discretion of the organisation rather than being influenced by external forces, such as unions or health and safety regulations (Dawley et al., 2008). These voluntary job rewards that come directly from the organisation are perceived as an indication that the organisation values employees' contribution made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being (Dawley et al., 2008). Therefore, a detailed exploration of the linkage between POS and affective commitment and job satisfaction in the lean production context would be of considerable interest, both theoretically and practically.

Influence of POS on the relationship between PDM and affective commitment and job satisfaction

The influence POS has on *affective commitment* has been corroborated by many studies in the organisational behaviour literature (e.g. Aube' et al., 2007; Rhoades et al., 2001). However, the strength of these relationships varies from one study to another (see the meta-analysis of Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002). In this regard, Aube' et al. (2007) argue that these variations in the effect size may depend on different moderating factors. However, we were unable to find any other studies that addressed the influence of POS on affective commitment in the context of lean production. Consistent with the findings of the past research in the field of organizational behaviour (such as Aube' et al., 2007; Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Rhoades et al., 2001), in this study we identify POS as a possible moderator that could influence the relationship between PDM and affective commitment. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed for this study.

Hypothesis 3: POS will moderate the positive relationship between PDM and affective commitment in such a way that affective commitment will be strengthened for a higher level of POS.

With regard to the relationship between POS and *job satisfaction*, several studies found that employees with a higher level of POS judge their jobs more favourably and in turn increase their level of job satisfaction (Eisenberger et al., 1997; Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Shanock and Eisenberger, 2006). In the context of high-performance work systems in manufacturing, Appelbaum et al. (2000) found a statistically significant positive relationship between opportunity to participate and job satisfaction in the steel industry. However, Appelbaum et al. (2000) did not find a statistically significant positive relationship between opportunity to participate and job satisfaction in the apparel and medical electronic instruments industries. Further, in the lean production context, Vidal (2007) concludes that participation does not necessarily lead to job satisfaction. However, these studies have not investigated whether POS plays an important role in moderating the effect of PDM on job satisfaction. Further, we were unable to find any other studies that addressed the influence of POS on job satisfaction in the context of lean production. Therefore, in this study we propose POS as a possible moderator that could influence the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction. The following hypothesis is proposed for this study.

Hypothesis 4: POS will moderate the positive relationship between PDM and job satisfaction in such a way that job satisfaction will be strengthened for a higher level of POS.

Figure 1 shows the hypothesised research model.

Take in Figure 1

Methodology

Sample

The target population for the study is a cross section of shop-floor employees engaged full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms, which have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and where lean production has become the standard of operation for at least one year in Sri Lanka. The following sample selection criteria were set for the study: 1) a firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) as it is the primary government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating both foreign and local investments in the country and export-apparel manufacturing is the major industrial category under BOI. Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 percent of their output. Thus, all export-apparel manufacturing firms that come under this study population are homogeneous in nature in terms of business operations; and 2) a firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function (not as a pilot project) and it should be the standard of operation for at least one year. This criterion was set as past researchers (e.g. Pirraglia et al., 2009) suggested the importance of distinguishing firms that have implemented lean and firms that are planning to implement, etc. Although there are nearly 800 firms engaged in the export-apparel manufacturing industry, in mid 2008, Wickramasinghe (2008) identified 12 BOI registered export-apparel manufacturing firms that had implemented lean production systems and running for at least one year. These 12 firms were considered as the population frame for this study and all the firms agreed to participate in the survey. To fulfil the expectations of this study, it was decided to collect data from shop-floor employees. Twelve contact persons were identified from each firm. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this paper randomly selected shop-floor employees to participate in the study. In doing so, attempts were made to select a cross-section of shop-floor employees from each firm. Further, participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. One thousand survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 5% of the total shop-floor employees in each firm. Of the total number of questionnaires distributed in March 2009, 625 responses were received. 616 usable responses resulted in a 62% response rate.

With regard to the characteristics of responding firms, the oldest firm was established in the year 1993 while the youngest firm was established in the year 2004. All the firms had adopted lean production methods after 2005, where the latest adoption occurred in two of the firms in the year 2007. When the firm size is measured in terms of average annual turnover in US\$ and the number of people employed, the respondent firms had an average annual turnover (in US\$) ranging from 50 to 250 Million while the total number of employees ranged from 300 to 5000. All the firms had a dedicated section to handle lean implementation headed by a senior level manager.

With regard to the characteristics of shop-floor employees, of the respondents (N=616), 59% were female while 41% were male. 64% were single while 36% were married. Mean age was 25 years (S.D.=4.84). Mean tenure in the present workplace was 4 years (S.D.=2.46). 67% had secondary education less than or equal to 10 years of full-time education while 33% had secondary education up to 13 years of full-time education as the highest level of education. 64% of the respondents came from organisations that had implemented lean production for 1 to 2.5 years while 36% came from organisations that had implemented lean production for more than 2.5 years.

Measures

Independent, dependent and moderator variables were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). In this regards, Kulas et al. (2008) found that the middle response category did not adversely affect reliability and validity in social research. For all measurement scales, standardized Cronbach's alpha was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al 2006). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for each construct (refer to Table 1).

Affective commitment was measured using the six items developed by Meyer et al. (1993). An example item includes “I feel a strong sense of belonging to the organisation”. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.715, Eigenvalue=2.52, and explained variation=69.13%.

Job satisfaction was measured using two items “Generally speaking, I am very satisfied with this job” and “I am generally satisfied with the kind of work I do” (Thatcher et al., 2002). Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.777, Eigenvalue=2.659, and explained variation=71.82%.

Perceived organisational support was measured using the eight-item short version of Eisenberger et al.’s (1997) POS scale. An example item includes “Help is available from my organisation when I have a problem”. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.760, Eigenvalue=2.895, and explained variation=73.16%.

Participation in decision making was measured by three items adapted from White and Ruh (1973). This scale was also used by Stashevsky and Elizur (2000) to analyse the effect of PDM on quality management. An example item includes “I have influence on decisions concerning my work group”. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.811, Eigenvalue=3.20, and explained variation=75.72%.

Although we intended to control characteristics of lean production (e.g. the reduction of work in progress, space, etc.) the firms were reluctant to provide these data. Therefore, the duration of lean production was selected as a control variable. The literature also suggests that the extent to which firms have adopted a lean production system may be influenced by the duration of lean production in operation (e.g. Browning and Heath, 2009; Conti et al., 2006). Therefore, the duration of lean production in operation, termed as “lean duration” in this study (in years), and five individual demographic characteristics (gender, marital status, education, age, and firm tenure) were controlled in the analysis. Of these individual demographic characteristics, gender (male-0, female-1), marital status (single-0, married-1) and the highest level of education (less than or equal to O/L-0, up to A/L-1) were binary coded while age and tenure were coded as continuous variables in years.

The measurement scales were previously used by Wickramasinghe (2008) in his study (N=284) on Sri Lankan export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka. Therefore, although the measures of constructs used in this study were developed in Western, English speaking countries these were used in our target industry in a previous study. Further, Wickramasinghe (2008) reports that measurement scales obtained standardised Cronbach's alpha values higher than 0.7, fulfilling the accepted guidelines proposed by Hair et al. (2006). Since target respondents may not have a good command of English, self-administered survey questionnaire was in the native language, *Sinhala*. We have used *Sinhala* translations of independent, dependent and moderator measurement scales from the study of Wickramasinghe (2008), for two reasons. First, Wickramasinghe (2008) assured the equivalence of the meaning of the measures that is used in the native language as he adhered to the guidelines stipulated in the literature (see Lynn, 2003). Second, these item scales were previously successfully tested in the same industrial sector by Wickramasinghe (2008) and were found to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Spector, 1994). However, Spector (1994) suggests that despite the weaknesses of the cross-sectional self-report methodology, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs, which can be useful for deriving hypotheses about how people react to jobs. Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al., 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003).

Data analysis procedure

Multivariate analysis of variance was conducted to check whether any group differences exist among the responses from the 12 firms for the four latent variables of the study. The results of the Wilks' Lambda statistics for the four variables revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) among the responses from the 12 firms.

Hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to test the moderation effect. The literature recommends that when the predictor and moderator variables are measured on a continuous scale, the hierarchical regression procedure that retains the continuous nature of the variables is preferred over using cut points (Aiken and West 1991). Therefore, hierarchical regression was used to test the hypothesised relationships (also refer to Fraizer et al., 2004). The variables were mean centred to increase interpretability of interactions (see Fraizer et al., 2004). The variables were entered into the regression equation in four steps. The control variables were entered in the first step, the independent variable was added in the second step, the moderator variable was added in the third step, and the interaction term was added in the fourth step (see Fraizer et al., 2004). The plots were constructed by plotting low, medium and high scores of the variables. For this, Jose's (2002) Excel version of ModGraph programme for continuous variables was used. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero.

Results

The means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations for the study variables are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table 1

The results for the moderator effect of POS on the relationship between PDM and affective commitment are shown in Table 2. As shown in Table 2 (Model 2), PDM is significantly

positively related to affective commitment ($p < .001$). This supports Hypothesis 1. As shown in Table 2 (Model 3), POS significantly impacts on affective commitment ($p < .001$). As indicated by the significant interaction term in Table 2 (Model 4), POS moderates the relationship between PDM and affective commitment. The plot that illustrates the moderation is shown in Figure 2. The results of simple effects test revealed that the relationship between PDM and affective commitment is moderated for high ($t = 4.083, p < .001$), medium ($t = 3.492, p < .001$) and low ($t = 3.847, p < .001$) levels of POS. This supports H3.

Take in Table 2

Take in Figure 2

The results for the moderator effect of POS on the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction are shown in Tables 3. As can be seen in Table 3 (Model 2), PDM is significantly positively related to job satisfaction ($p < .001$). This supports Hypothesis 2. As shown in Table 2 (Model 3), POS significantly impacts on job satisfaction ($p < .001$). As indicated by the significant interaction term in Table 3 (Model 4), POS moderates the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction. The plot that illustrates the moderation is shown in Figure 3. The results of simple effects test revealed that the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction is moderated for high ($t = 4.344, p < .001$), medium ($t = 3.352, p < .001$) and low ($t = 2.843, p < .01$) levels of POS. This supports H4.

Take in Table 3

Take in Figure 3

Discussion, conclusions and implications

This study investigated the moderating effect of POS on the relationship between PDM and affective commitment, and PDM and job satisfaction in the lean production in Sri Lanka. Based on the literature reviewed earlier, we have developed four hypotheses to test whether POS moderates the positive relationship between PDM and affective commitment, and PDM and job satisfaction in such a way that affective commitment and job satisfaction will be strengthened for a higher level of POS. For the investigation, we have used widely accepted multiple parameters drawn from the literature reviewed earlier to evaluate PDM, POS, affective commitment, and job satisfaction. The item scales are shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. This supports claims made by Wickramasinghe (2008) that the measures seem to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

We have drawn a random sample of 616 shop-floor employees from 12 export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and lean production has become the standard of operation for at least one year in Sri Lanka. When comparing our study with the earlier study conducted by Wickramasinghe (2008), he surveyed 284 shop-floor employees from 6 out of the above 12 firms and reported significant positive correlations between PDM, POS, job satisfaction and affective commitment. Of the four hypotheses developed to test the moderation effect in our study two were directly evolved from the previous study. That is, PDM will be positively related to affective commitment and PDM will be positively related to job satisfaction. The findings of the present study for these two hypotheses supported the findings of Wickramasinghe's (2008) study. When the findings relating to these two hypotheses are compared with other previous studies, behavioural scientists pointing to the evidence of the lack of commitment, low job satisfaction, and the restriction of productivity in traditional plants have argued for increased opportunities for employees to participate at work (e.g. Mulder, 1971). Subsequent research within the organisational behaviour literature provides support that PDM increases affective commitment (e.g. Scott-Ladd et al., 2006) and job satisfaction (e.g. Witt et al., 2000). However, PDM is an integral aspect of lean production. In lean production settings, where excess

inventory or other buffers are not available to counter production or quality failures, employees must have the ability, willingness, and authority to make decisions. Such lean characteristics can only be successfully achieved through employee participation. However, there is surprisingly little empirical research addressing PDM in the operations management literature. Although previous research in the context of lean production suggests that an increased level of employee participation does not necessarily increase their job satisfaction (e.g. Vidal, 2007), we found that PDM increases job satisfaction and affective commitment. Therefore, the positive relationship between PDM and job satisfaction, and PDM and affective commitment found in this study lends credence to previous research findings within the organisational behaviour literature (e.g. Scott-Ladd et al., 2006). The findings imply that when an individual becomes more involved in the accomplishment of work through PDM, it leads to increased individual integration into the organisation and job satisfaction.

The present study extended the earlier study (i.e., Wickramasinghe, 2008) by examining the moderating effect of POS in the relationship between PDM and affective commitment, and PDM and job satisfaction. The results of the study revealed that the relationship between PDM and affective commitment is moderated by POS, and that the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction is moderated by POS. When the findings relating to these two hypotheses are compared with past studies, the support for the employee from the organisation is identified as an important part of the organisational milieu that concerns the commitment of the organisation to employees (Eisenberger et al., 1986). It is found that POS moderates the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction. This implies that, in the lean production setting where employees have little alternative choice instead of participating in job related decision making, support from the employer for employees' substantive job related decision-making and problem-solving may buffer the relationship between PDM and job satisfaction. It is also found that POS moderates the relationship between PDM and affective commitment. Affective commitment represents an employee's attachment to and identification with the organisation, and individuals with a high level of affective commitment continue to work for the organisation because they want to. The findings suggest that employees may interpret, on the one hand, the

support provided by their employer as a demonstration of commitment towards them for their contributions to the functioning of the organisation, which fulfils the employees' need for esteem, approval and affiliation (see Eisenberger et al., 1986). On the other hand, the support provided by their employer may appear to be interpreted by employees as a mark of respect and consideration on the part of their employer, which influence employees to enhance their sense of belonging to and pride in the organisation (see Meyer et al., 1993). Therefore, POS operates to strengthen the relationship between PDM and affective commitment.

Affective commitment and job satisfaction are two outcomes desired by employees just as PDM is a desired outcome for employers, especially, in the lean production context. Therefore, the findings presented in this paper would be valuable for academics and practitioners alike. On the one hand, the findings of our study contribute to the operations management literature by examining widely accepted concepts in the organisational behaviour literature to the context of lean production. It should be noted that there is surprisingly little empirical research addressing human dimension in the operations management literature. We have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated the links proposed in this study in the context of lean production or advanced manufacturing systems to make straight forward comparisons. Therefore, more empirical work is needed to test our propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article. Therefore, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. On the other hand, practitioners need valid information to guide their actions in enhancing employee participation and the quality of work life. Lean production allows decision making to be decentralised. However, individual work preferences, for instance, the nature of participation, problems that employees involve in solving, and control employees enjoy over decisions are context dependent. It could be assumed that employees may evaluate work arrangements and adapt to given situations, particularly when they perceive little alternative choice. Therefore, practitioners could determine whether changes in POS are required to enhance the influence of PDM on affective commitment and job satisfaction. This is vital in lean production, which is dependent on human control of product quality and

productivity. Therefore, the findings may be helpful in maintaining a balance between employees' and employers' needs, especially, in the long-term where PDM could be viewed merely as a survival strategy for coping with work in lean production, neglecting employees' affective commitment and job satisfaction.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

First, although we intended to include constructs of lean production as controls in our model, we faced difficulties in collecting these secondary data from all firms that participated in the survey. Hence, we had to limit the variables that explain lean production to lean duration. Second, as information about early respondents, late respondents and non-respondents to the survey questionnaire has not been recoded, it is difficult to know whether there are any differences within these three categories. Third, the study was confined to the export-apparel industry in Sri Lanka. However, it should be noted that lean production practices are not yet well established in other industrial and service sectors compared to the export-apparel industry in the country. Fourth, the interrelationships between affective commitment and job satisfaction are beyond the focus of this study and have not been explored as a result. Therefore, future studies can incorporate such relationships using path analysis techniques.

With regard to specific areas for future research, first, more future research studies in different samples and longitudinal studies are necessary to compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data to validate the links proposed in this study. Second, future research could extend data collection by including managers, team leaders, human resource managers etc., who are actively involved in the lean production process. Third, future studies could extend the investigation by evaluating other variables of interest using path analysis techniques. For instance, future research could investigate the effect of POS on organisational citizenship behaviour. Overall, more empirical studies are needed on how shop-floor employees participating in decision making in manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems respond to their work arrangements and the organisation.

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Figures

Figure 1: Hypothesised research model

Figure 2: Moderation effects- affective commitment moderated by POS

Figure 3: Moderation effects- job satisfaction moderated by POS

Tables

Table 1 Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Gender ^a	1.59	.49	1								
2 Age	1.49	.65	.096**	1							
3 Marital status ^a	1.65	.48	.032	-.389**	1						
4 Education ^a	1.49	.60	-.015	.035	.149**	1					
5 Tenure	2.93	.90	-.076*	.394**	-.170**	.105**	1				
6 Lean duration	2.15	.47	-.259**	-.006	-.151**	.009	.160**	1			
7 PDM ^b	3.79	.53	-.084*	.152**	-.045	.124**	.099**	.148**	1		
8 POS ^b	3.93	.56	.106**	.046	-.065	.022	.005	.025	.472**	1	
9 Affective commitment ^b	4.32	.54	.094**	.101**	-.070	.035	.036	.075*	.490**	.450**	1
10 Job satisfaction ^b	4.07	.60	.234**	.120**	-.120*	.030	.001	.111**	.498**	.405**	.380**

Note. ** Significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed). * Significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables

^b Values of skewness ranged between 0.17(lowest) to 0.25 (highest). Values of kurtosis ranged between 0.01 (lowest) to 0.27 (highest).

Table 2: Results of hierarchical regression analysis for affective commitment

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Control</i>				
Gender	.088	.081	.017	.015
Age	.024	.033	.051	.051
Marital status	-.044	-.036	-.027	-.026
Education	.022	.062	.077	.076
Tenure	.037	.043	.099*	.100*
Lean duration	.157**	.036	.093*	.092*
<i>Step 2: Independent</i>				
PDM		.502***	.247***	.646***
<i>Step 3: Moderator</i>				
POS			.258***	.730***
<i>Step 4: Interaction term</i>				
PDM x POS				.692***
R ² (Adj.)	.030	.269	.521	.572
F change	2.641*	17.704***	42.585***	49.228***
ΔR ²	.048	.285	.534	.575

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<.001

Table 3: Results of hierarchical regression analysis for job satisfaction

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Control</i>				
Gender	.007	.014	.075	.090
Age	.047	.038	.021	.024
Marital status	-.062	-.055	-.046	-.040
Education	.012	.027	.041	.033
Tenure	.061	.055	.001	.010
Lean duration	.348***	.229***	.114*	.106*
<i>Step 2: Independent</i>				
PDM		.496***	.302***	.515***
<i>Step 3: Moderator</i>				
POS			.484***	.740***
<i>Step 4: Interaction term</i>				
PDM x POS				.395***
R ² (Adj.)	.008	.342	.497	.585
F change	4.29	24.583***	50.524***	54.856***
ΔR ²	.024	.356	.500	.597

* p<0.05, *** p<.001